

PROJECT

Valorising Stress-Resilient Tomato Landraces

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The potential of tomato landraces to increase farming sustainability

Tomato is the world's largest vegetable crop (>130 Mt and growing). The EU is among the biggest producers, with a major contribution by southern countries; EU citizens consume 20 kg of fruits per capita and year, both as fresh and processed products. Since tomatoes are rich in carotenoids, this significantly contributes to our antioxidant uptake. However, extensive inbreeding during early domestication limited the genetic variation of modern cultivars below 5%.

This **domestication syndrome** makes the most cultivated tomato varieties particularly sensitive to drought stress, a major threat to growers under changing climate conditions. It also increases the tomato crop environmental footprint, lowering its sustainability.

Methodology

The research group at UNITO has been working on several EU projects aiming at identifying and characterising accessions of Mediterranean crops resilient to environmental stress. Namely, tomato landraces resilient to drought stress have been identified; however, **resilience is not necessarily matched by standard fruit characteristics and field performances**, which may hinder acceptance by both farmers and consumers. To facilitate it:

At the farm:

Farmers will be assisted in growing the landraces under reduced resource input.

At the marketplace:

Consumers will be informed about the sustainability of the products and the health benefits of a diversified diet.

RADIANT

In RADIANT, joint efforts of UNITO and a local farmer will promote co-innovation around underutilised, drought-resilient tomato landraces. The farmer plans to use the landraces to increase diversity in his production, which reaches final consumers directly. This will implement a first, local and short but **dynamic value chain** around these underutilised landraces.

PROJECT

Greenhouse trials on the performances of tomato landraces under stress (previous projects TOMRES/H2020 and VEG-ADAPT/PRIMA)

Valorising tomato landraces as tools for increased crop sustainability and diversity

Within RADIANT, the joint work by UNITO and a local tomato grower with direct access to consumers will give life to a “living lab”, *i.e.* a user-centred, iterative, open-innovation ecosystem, integrating concurrent research and innovation processes within a public-private-people partnership.